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MARINA
**Marine Knowledge Sharing Platform for Federating
Responsible Research and Innovation Communities**

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*Individual Report of the local Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
workshop R2*

CNR - IRPPS

Rome

Italy

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MML WORKSHOP	DETAILS
Date	14/03/2018
Duration	From 14:30 to 18:30
Location	Italy, Rome
Title of workshop in English	What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?
Title of workshop in native language	Come sarà il trasporto marittimo nel 2050? Trasporti marittimi: quali le sfide in termini di ricerca e innovazione responsabile?
Marine challenge that the workshop has tackled	Sea Transportation
Number of participants	14
Type of workshop (<i>local or international</i>)	local
Round (<i>first or second</i>)	second
Selected methodology (<i>Focus Group, World Café, Science Café, Delphi, Structured Democratic Dialogue Process, Future Search, etc.</i>)	Other
Language of the workshop	Italian
Name of the organizing institution	CNR - IRPPS
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1 Purpose of the report

The purpose of this report is to describe the local Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop *What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?* That was hosted by CNR – IRPPS in Rome in Italy on 14th March 2018. The workshop addressed Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) actions that should be put in place to reduce the impacts of maritime transport on the atmosphere with greenhouse gas emissions and on the sea with polluting emissions (tanks washing, fuel spills, etc ...), on the quality life in port cities' (traffic, pollutants emission in proximity of the houses, etc. ...), on the mobility of people, and the development of tourism.

The report describes the results of the workshop and the feedback by the participants. It includes a general outline and international background of the MARINA pan-European MML process of stakeholder engagement in marine and maritime issues and Responsible Research and Innovation; the facilitation methodology; the participant recruitment and the follow-up actions.

The results of the workshop will nourish the second round of the international MML workshops scheduled in the first half of 2018; provide input for the roadmap of Responsible Research and Innovation good practice as well as recommendations about embedding the RRI in the policy-making processes. The will be assembled with the outputs of other local MML workshops in a comprehensive report that will be submitted to the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission.

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3 Executive Summary

On 14th March 2018 CNR – IRPPS organised in Rome (Italy) the second local Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop titled “What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?”. The workshop sought to address Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) actions that should be put in place to reduce the impacts of maritime transport on the atmosphere with greenhouse gas emissions and on the sea with polluting emissions (tanks washing, fuel spills, etc ...), on the quality life in port cities (traffic, pollutants emission in proximity of the houses, etc. ...), on the mobility of people, and the development of economic and cultural assets of the interested areas.

The event was held in the framework of the MARINA project and is part of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning process consisting of two phases of workshops at local and international levels. The process has been activated engaging scientists and research actors, civil society, businesses and policy-makers in a participatory debate to discussing how Responsible Research and Innovation can help to address the current marine and societal challenges and unlock the potential for Blue Growth in marine and coastal areas of the European Union.

The half day-long workshop was facilitated according to the steps used for Science Cafè (as specified in <http://www.caffescienza.it/> and http://www.cafescientifique.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=72&Itemid=484). However, as the MML workshop was held in a room that is located in the building of the National Research Council in Rome (and it was not used the location of a Cafè as usually do science café events).For this reason we classify the used method as “Other”. The used method allowed us to collect contributions from individuals with different views, backgrounds and perspectives through a process that is inclusive and collaborative. Participants were scientists, experts and people not typically get involved with scientific discussions. After a short presentation of some participants, providing different perspectives of the addressed questions, participants were encouraged to discuss empowering common knowledge and mutual learning.

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Fourteen participants were recruited based on their expertise and interest in maritime transportation.

After some [presentations](#) (available on the marina platform) participants started to discuss of the issues presented in the hot topic and the presentations from the experts. After this discussion, and based on the triggering question that the facilitator did, participants proposed and discussed their ideas of Responsible Research and Innovation actions. Based on these ideas a roadmap has been developed on how sustainable maritime transportation could contribute to competitive and sustainable coastal and maritime tourism in Europe.

The [workshop was webcast on the MARINA platform](#).

The chief message was the importance of maritime and integrated transportation for sustainability at environmental, cultural and socio-economic level. It was underlined that any research and innovation can have significant impact in the complexity of political, scientific and regulatory issues (at local, national and European level, and including countries of Mediterranean area) stimulating a dialogue among the different stakeholder groups:

- the general public and students to contribute in improving a common understanding and awareness of potentialities that gulfs, harbours and well-preserved coastal marine environment represent for the economy and culture of a territory,
- business and industry professionals to develop and use innovative technologies socially and environmentally acceptable to reduce environmental risks, to improve communication among the different authorities, providing decision support systems,
- scientists to bring responses to sustainable transportation challenges and finally policy-makers to reinforce policies and adopt coherent legislative frameworks and funding to design, plan and fund and interconnected transportation system (maritime and terrestrial).

4 Engaging societal actors in Responsible Research and Innovation for smart sustainable and inclusive Blue Growth in Europe

4.1 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshops

The local workshop [What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?](#) was held in the framework of the MARINA project. It was organised by CNR - IRPPS in Rome, Italy on 14th March 2018. The workshop has been part of the second round of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Process composed of two phases of workshops at local and international levels and connected to the international Responsible Research and Innovation practitioner and policy-maker event. The process is schematised in Fig.1.

Fig.1. MARINA Mobilisation and Mutual Learning process

The workshop:

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1. Engaged European societal actors in a multi-actor dialogue and in co-creating a participatory roadmap of actions for tackling the marine societal challenge of sea transportation and based on Responsible and Innovation principles;
2. Started the process of federating Civil Society Organisations (CSOs), citizens, businesses, industry, research, policy-makers and communicators face-to-face and on-line;
3. Set in motion inclusive mechanisms for sharing knowledge and best practice, building common understanding and co-creating solutions to marine societal challenges and based them on the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation;
4. Facilitated federation of communities and networks on the MARINA digital platform.

4.2 How can Responsible Research and Innovation ensure a smart, sustainable and inclusive Blue Growth in Europe?

Europe is facing “innovation emergency”: it spends 0.8% of GDP less than the USA and 1.5% less than Japan on Research & Development (R&D) every year. Thousands of European best researchers and innovators have moved to countries where conditions are more favourable¹, despite the support by the European Union to foster research and innovation in terms of networking, funding², social business, start-up, dissemination and incubation³. Therefore, in 2018, the European Commission will increase the support of smart and inclusive growth with €76.5 billion in commitments and €66.4 billion in payments, i.e. up by 2.1% and 17.5% respectively compared to 2017.

Seas and oceans are drivers of the European economy and have great potential for innovation and growth. They can contribute to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.

Accordingly, the European Union has set out the Blue Growth⁴ long-term strategy to support sustainable development in the marine and maritime sectors in Europe. This strategy aims to boost growth in areas such as aquaculture, coastal tourism, marine biotechnology, ocean energy and seabed mining. It puts forward three priorities to make Europe a smarter, more sustainable and more inclusive place to live:

- Smart growth, through the development of an economy based on knowledge, research and innovation;
- Sustainable growth, through the promotion of resource-efficient, green and competitive markets;
- Inclusive growth, through policies aimed at fostering job creation and poverty reduction⁵.

At a global level, in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, social challenges are a priority for a sustainable growth⁶.

[Responsible Research and Innovation](#) is a key cross-cutting instrument to reach these goals, an investment for our future. In practice, it is implemented as a package that includes multi-actor and public engagement in research and innovation, thanks to open access to scientific results, formal and informal science education and the take up of gender and ethics in the research and innovation content and process.

¹<http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union>

²Employment and Social Innovation Programme, Horizon 2020, SME Instrument, Collective Awareness Platforms, EU structural and investment funds - Guide to Social Innovation. Social Challenges Platform.

³https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/innovation/policy/social_it

⁴https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy/blue_growth_en

⁵http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Smarter,_greener,_more_inclusive_-_indicators_to_support_the_Europe_2020_strategy

⁶“Sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth is essential for prosperity. [...] We will work to build dynamic, sustainable, innovative and people-centered economies, promoting youth employment and women’s economic empowerment, in particular, and decent work for all.”

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Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (Von Schomberg, 2011). The European Commission distinguishes 6 key dimensions of RRI: Public Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality, Governance and Ethics.⁷

Public and multi-stakeholder engagement is a societal commitment to provide encouragement, opportunities and competencies that will empower citizens and civil society organisations to participate in research and innovation. It is also about bringing together a diversity of actors from research community, policy-making, business and industry, who would not normally interact with each other, on matters of science and technology.⁸

Science Education aims at increasing society's appetite for innovation and interest in science, in particular among young people with a special emphasis on girls. It encourages innovative pedagogies to teach science, the involvement of institutions that organize such activities, promotes RRI in higher education curricula and eases access to scientific careers.⁹

Open access and open science intend to make research findings, data, scientific publications and information available free of charge for anyone.

Gender Equality aims at removing barriers that generate discrimination against women in scientific careers and decision-making. It fosters gender balance in research teams and integrates a gender dimension in research and innovation content in order to improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and innovation.¹⁰

Ethics is given the highest priority in the European Union funded research and innovation. It implies the application of fundamental ethical principles and legislation to scientific research and innovation in all possible domains and includes the avoidance of any breach of research integrity and ethics dumping.¹¹

Governance is the umbrella for all other dimensions. It addresses the responsibility of policy makers to prevent harmful or unethical developments in research and innovation and developing harmonious models for Responsible Research and Innovation that integrate Public and multi-stakeholder Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality and Ethics.¹²

The Blue Growth strategy reflects policy priorities. It aims at bringing together resources and knowledge across different fields, technologies and disciplines, including social sciences and the humanities by addressing the following challenges:

- Health, demographic change and wellbeing;
- Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy;
- Secure, clean and efficient energy;
- Smart, green and integrated transport;
- Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials;
- Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies;
- Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens.

7 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

8 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/766>

9 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/795>

10 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/797>

11 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/767>

12 https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_public_engagement/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf

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4.3 The MARINA workshops and Sustainable Development Goals

The European Union's response to the 2030 agenda of the United Nations Organisation is "The new European consensus on development of 'our world, our dignity, our future'". The document highlights that "the EU and its Member States will integrate the respect of human rights, democracy, the rule of law and gender equality into their political dialogue" and that "sustainable development requires a holistic and cross-sector policy approach and is ultimately an issue of governance which needs to be pursued in partnership with all stakeholders and on all levels"¹³. Accordingly, the topics addressed at the MARINA workshops have been related to Sustainable Development Goals¹⁴ such as:

- SD Goal 1: End poverty in all its forms everywhere;
- SD Goal 4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all;
- SD Goal 6: Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all;
- SD Goal 7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all;
- SD Goal 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all;
- SD Goal 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation;
- SD Goal 11: Make cities and human settlements safe, resilient and sustainable;
- SD Goal 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns;
- SD Goal 13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts;
- SD Goal 14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources;
- SD Goal 17: Strengthen means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development.

4.4 The choice of the workshop marine topic

The marine challenges and the topics of the workshops in the second round stemmed from international and national agendas. They have been: marine biotechnologies, sea transportation, deep-sea mining, renewable energy (wind, wave and tidal) and marine changes caused by climate.

The participants of the workshop "What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?" in Rome, Italy discussed the marine challenge of sea transportation in the perspective of Responsible Research and Innovation. The triggering question to address this issue was "What actions are necessary to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level?". In response to it, they put one or more proposals of participatory RRI-driven actions.

5 What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?

5.1 The current situation

The Mediterranean Basin has been playing a crucial role for communication of people around it, stimulating the birth and growth of magnificent civilizations. Indeed, flourishing cultures were born all around the Basin, from east to west, from north to south, from Mesopotamia to Egypt, from Anatolia, Troy to Macedonia, from the Greek

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/european-consensus-on-development-final-20170626_en.pdf

¹⁴ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org>

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city states to Phoenician civilization, from Carthage to Rome, from Baghdad to Al-Andalus, from Byzantium to the Ottoman Empire and from Alexandria to Venice. (<https://unchronicle.un.org/article/mediterranean-sea-cradle-civilization>). All these civilizations took advantage from unique. Currently, Mediterranean Sea continues playing its key role for the cultural, social, economic and political development of its countries. Maritime transport is one of the key factors of this development, but, at the same time, is also causes of environmental issues. From the environmental point of view, although the emissions of greenhouse gases by maritime transport are lower than the emissions generated by road or air transport, a significant increase is expected in the coming years. According to an estimate by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), the emissions of greenhouse gases produced by maritime transport will increase by 250% by 2050 and they will reach 17% of global emissions. This is the forecast if changes do not occur in this sector that largely uses more polluting fossil fuels (poorly refined mixtures) for the power supply of the motors.

What about other impacts such as abrasion (the damage caused from anchoring ships) and underwater noise? In particular in the Ligurian Sea excessive noise makes it hard for cetaceans to communicate to receive warning and detect approaching vessels and other hazards. (Ameer Abdulla, and Olof Linden, Maritime Traffic Effects on Biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea, Vol. 1, 2008 - https://cmsdata.iucn.org/downloads/maritime_v1_lr.pdf)

For this reason, measures such as slowing down the navigation speed are already suggested and adopted. Areas of controlling sulphur emissions and other types of controls are defined. Also work is being done to improve the efficiency of the fuel consumption and the use of cleaner fuels. Starting in 2020, a new maximum threshold for the amount of sulphur allowed in fuels will be globally introduced, limiting the concentration to 0.5%.

The pollution produced by maritime transport has a major impact on the health of the planet, on a local, regional and international level.

From the economic and societal point of view, sea transport represents a very important sector for carrying goods because it is cheaper than other types of transport and it represents an important driving force for many sectors. In particular “Marine assets in the Mediterranean Sea generate much more value than we are aware of and could provide even more if well managed.” (<https://d2ouvy59podg6k.cloudfront.net/downloads/economy.pdf>). “Mediterranean sea generates an annual economic value of US\$ 450 billion”. However, the importance of Mediterranean cannot be reduced only to its economic value, but its value (as already explained) is connected with society, with environment, culture and common values of people of the Med countries. (https://www.ansa.it/documents/1506517281253_wwf_REVIVING-MED-ECO_web_embargoed.pdf)

In Italy, in 2017 the maritime transport of goods increased in terms of tons of 3.4%. Italy ranks third in the maritime transport of goods; it is preceded by the United Kingdom and the Netherlands (Italian Statistical Yearbook 2017 - related to the year 2015).

In Lazio region, there are different and very relevant harbours both for goods and people transport, such as the Civitavecchia and the Fiumicino harbours.

The economy of the city of Civitavecchia has been always based on its harbour activities; it is currently the first cruise harbour in Italy (and the second in Europe after Barcelona) with over 2.3 million of cruise passengers; it is a reference point for the national tourism thanks to its proximity to high-speed rail networks. Thanks to the new development plans, the harbour of Civitavecchia has also increased its commercial traffic, reaching a total of two million tons. The harbour of Civitavecchia is an important node of the ferry network with destinations to various European and African countries bordering the Mediterranean, thus being strategic for accessing to important tourist destinations.

The harbour of Fiumicino is mainly used for fishing, tourism, transportation of raw minerals and oil due to the proximity of the processing plants and refineries within the territories. With over 8,600 berths and over 200 spots

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for mega-yachts, Lazio has a good position in the yachting sector in Italy considering the economic potential of this sector that is strongly connected to tourism.

Within the workshop, the issues related to the actions that can be identified to reduce the impact of maritime transport on the environment, the safety of operators, the quality life of citizens and the planning of infrastructures required for the transport of goods and people will be discussed.

5.2 The triggering question: What actions are necessary to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transportation and increase safety levels?

Maritime transportation can have different kinds of impacts: on the atmosphere with greenhouse gas emissions and on the sea with polluting emissions (tanks washing, fuel spills, etc.), on the quality life in port cities' (traffic, pollutants emission in proximity of the houses, etc.); the mobility of people, and the development of tourism and other economic activities.

Maritime transport is a cross-cutting topic between maritime pollution, air pollution, planning of ports and connected infrastructures, citizens' quality life (in the cities with ports, tourists, etc.). In this context, Responsible Research and Innovation (in processes, products, services and technologies) can provide a valuable approach for finding solutions to overcome the current marine and societal challenges unlocking the potential for Blue Growth. The six RRI dimensions (public and multi-stakeholder Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality, Ethics, Governance) and environment protection, are the elements of a framework for allowing societal values and expectations as well as environment to be taken into account in the process of reducing negative impacts of marine transportation, reinforcing potentialities of its innovations.

At the beginning of the workshop some of the participants provided a presentation sharing their knowledge and experience. After these presentations the participants were asked to define actions related to the Hot topic and RRI. Some participants decided to elaborate jointly the action that they proposed (if they came for the same organization), two participants, due to their role in their organization contributed to the workshop providing their knowledge on the current status, but they did not propose any specific action, as this required for them an authorization from their organization. The ten actions proposed are the following:

- *Action 1 - Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and Railway development for freight transport in ports (2 votes);* the focus of this action is on the integration of maritime transport with the land transport system.
- *Action 2 - Sharing of infrastructures and information (1 vote);* designing infrastructural solutions also using ICT tools and databases from different sources to share a new demand for maritime and non-maritime transport from a sustainability perspective.
- *Action 3 - Improving/developing Technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (3 votes);* the safe by design approach helps to integrate safety and innovation of technological solutions that will be developed in the transportation sectors.
- *Action 4 - Implementation of a decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (3 votes);* different dimensions and parameters needs to be considered for including multidisciplinary and the different stakeholders' competences in a decision process.
- *Action 5 - Promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors. (6 votes);* this aims sharing a common strategy for policies involving research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors.
- *Action 6 - Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine*

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environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy (5 votes); a strong education process will build a common and wide different actors' collective awareness of on the importance of marine environment and marine transportation for society, culture, economy and environment.

- Action 7 - Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery (5 votes); the goal of this action is to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic development. This means that it is important to organize events, tables of discussion and networking events at any level to establish this collaboration.
- Action 8 - Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies (3 votes); this action will involve universities, companies, students for promoting the arising of innovative ideas.
- Action 9 - Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services (4 votes)
- Action 10 - Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks (2 votes); some technologies already experimented can be widely used for protecting the environment and potentially dangerous cargo.

The actions are detailed explained in appendix 1.

The ten actions have been classified in three clusters (Fig.2):

1. *Technological solutions*, with four actions classified in this cluster
2. *Knowledge sharing and support systems*, with five actions classified in this cluster, and
3. *Education - Awareness*, with one action classified in this cluster.

Cluster 1 – **Technological solutions**

The actions of the cluster **Technological solutions** are mainly related to the development of technological solutions to support the design, the evaluation and integration of maritime transportation systems and at improving the safety and efficiency of maritime transport systems.

The actions (Fig.2) collected a total number of 10 votes with an average value of 2,5 votes/action. Furthermore, the actions of the cluster are associated nine times to RRI dimensions with an average value of 2,25 RRI dimensions/action (this average value has been computed by summing the RRI dimensions implied in each action divided for number of action in the cluster). The relevant RRI dimensions are Open Access (four actions), Public Engagement and Governance (two actions), and Ethics (one action).

The actions of the cluster **Technological solutions** are mainly addressed to the following stakeholders: Researchers & Academia and Business/Industry (4 actions), followed by citizens/CSOs/NGOs with 3 actions and Policy makers & implementers with 2 actions.

Finally, the actions of the cluster contribute to the challenge “*Smart, green and integrated transport*” with 3 actions, followed by “*Secure, clean and efficient energy*” and “*Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials*” with 2 actions. Only one action contributes to “*Health, demographic change and wellbeing*”, “*Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy*”, and “*Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens*”. No action addresses “*Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies*”.

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Fig.2. Clusters of the actions proposed during the local MML workshop in Rome, Italy

Cluster 2 – Knowledge sharing and support systems

The actions of the cluster **Technological solutions** are mainly related to actions for promoting collaboration among stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors, for sharing of infrastructures and information, promoting actions

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and collaboration among stakeholders at transnational level, and developing decision support tools based on information using automated action systems that would assist decision makers in managing critical events.

The actions (Fig.2) collected a total number of 19 votes with an average value of 3,8 votes/action. Furthermore, the actions of the cluster are associated thirteen times to RRI dimensions with an average value of 2,6 RRI dimensions/action (this average value has been computed by summing the RRI dimensions implied in each action divided for number of action in the cluster). The relevant RRI dimensions are Open Access, Public Engagement and Governance (4 actions), followed by Science Education (1 action).

The actions of the cluster **Technological solutions** are mainly addressed to the following stakeholders: Researchers & Academia and Policy makers & implementers (5 actions), followed by citizens/CSOs/NGOs and Business/Industry with 4 actions.

Finally, the actions of the cluster contribute to the challenge “*Smart, green and integrated transport*”, followed by “*Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies*” with 3 actions and “*Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens*” and “*Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy*” with 2 actions. Only one action contributes to “*Secure, clean and efficient energy*” and “*Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials*”. No action addresses “*Health, demographic change and wellbeing*”.

Cluster 3 – Education – Awareness

The action of the cluster **Education – Awareness** are mainly related to actions for promoting education and awareness at all level with the objective to educate for reducing environmental impact of maritime transport and to better understand the importance of the marine environment for the socio-economic development of Italy.

The action (Fig.2) collected a total number of 5 votes with an average value of 5 votes/action. Furthermore, the action of the cluster is associated to four RRI dimensions: Open Access, Public Engagement, Science Education and Governance.

The actions of the cluster **Technological solutions** are mainly addressed to the following stakeholders: Researchers & Academia, Policy makers & implementers, citizens/CSOs/NGOs and Business/Industry.

Finally, the actions of the cluster contribute to the challenge “*Smart, green and integrated transport*”, “*Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy*”, “*Secure, clean and efficient energy*”, and “*Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies*”. The action do not address “*Health, demographic change and wellbeing*”, “*Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials*”, and “*Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens*”

5.3 Building a roadmap

The Final Influence Map has been defined analysing the outcomes of the workshop and the discussion of the stakeholders. The map consists of three levels and includes the actions that had the capacity to influence others or, their achievement depends on the implementation of other actions independently from the received number of votes.

The actions at the bottom level 3 (L3) sustain the achievement of the actions at upper levels up to the ultimate level 1 of *Promote actions at trans-national level* (Action 5, Cluster 2, Level 1, Votes 6). This action was one of the two most important ones with six votes. .

The six actions at level 3 (L3) lay foundations for other initiatives and come from the clusters *Technological solutions*(C1) and *Knowledge sharing and support systems* (C2). At level 2 (L2) three actions: *Sharing of*

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infrastructures and information (A2, C2, L2, V1), Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (A3, C1, L2, V3), and Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level (A6, C3, L2, V5) belong to the cluster Knowledge sharing and support systems (C2), Technological solutions (C1), and Education – Awareness (C3), respectively. This contributes to reaching the level 1 and the ultimate goal of Promote actions at trans-national level (A5, C2, L1, V6).

It is worth noting that the actions of Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports (A1, C1, L3, V2), Development of information-based decision support tools (A9, C2, L3, V4) and Implementation of decision systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (A4, C2, L3, V3) strongly influence two actions at level 2 (L2): the Sharing of infrastructures and information (A2, C2, L2, V1) and the improvement/development of technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (A3, C2, L2, V3), which in turn stimulate the ultimate goal of Promoting actions at trans-national level (A5, C2, L1, V6).

Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population (A7, C2, L3, V5) supports the Sharing of infrastructures and information (A2, C2, L2, V1), while Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks (A10, C1, L3, V2), and Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies (A8, C1, L3, V3) contribute to the improvement/development of Technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (A3, C2, L2, V3).

The influence map indicates a strong need for education and collaboration at all levels (Public Engagement, Science Education). Even though there are strong influences among actions and levels, the roadmap can be taken up at any point and several actions can take place simultaneously on several levels.

Fig.3. Final influence map of the actions proposed during the local MML workshop in Rome, Italy

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WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision			
TO ENSURE MARINE TRANSPORTATION SECURITY FOR PRESENT AND FUTURE GENERATIONS TO REDUCE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF MARITIME TRANSPORT AND INCREASE SAFETY LEVEL			
WHO	WHAT	WHEN	OVERALL GOAL
Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs Business/Industry Researchers & Academia Policy makers & implementers Other (Please specify)	Action	How long will it take to complete the action / when will it be reached: short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 y), long term (over 5 y)	Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from: Health, democratic change and well-being Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT ¹⁵			
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports(2 votes)	LT	Health, democratic change and well-being Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers	Sharing of infrastructures and information (1 vote)	LT	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Smart, green and integrated transport

¹⁵Involvement of the widest possible diversity of actors and their joint participation in co-creating the future : <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

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			Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors (6 votes)	ST	Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
SCIENCE EDUCATION			
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy

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Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	for the socio-economic development of Italy (5 votes)		Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
OPEN ACCESS			
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports (2 votes)	LT	Health, democratic change and well-being Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry	Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies (3 votes)	ST	Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers	Sharing of infrastructures and information (1 vote)	LT	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and

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Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks (2 votes)	MT & LT	reflective societies Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Smart, green and integrated transport
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services (4 votes)	ST & MT	Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport

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			Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
GENDER EQUALITY			
GOVERNANCE			
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports (2 votes)	LT	Health, democratic change and well-being Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers	Sharing of infrastructures and information (1 vote)	LT	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (3 votes)	LT	Smart, green and integrated transport Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services (4 votes)	ST & MT	Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies Secure societies - Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy

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implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy (5 votes)		Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Policy makers & implementers Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery (5 votes)	ST	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Secure, clean and efficient energy Smart, green and integrated transport Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
ETHICS			
Researchers & Academia Business/Industry Citizens/CSOs/NGOs	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks (2 votes)	MT & LT	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy Smart, green and integrated transport
OTHER (please specify)			

Fig.4. Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Rome, Italy

6 Sea transportation and Responsible Research and Innovation

6.1 How do the results relate to the RRI dimensions?

This section will analyse the actions suggested by the workshop participants in the framework of six dimensions of Responsible Research and Innovation: Public and Multi-stakeholder Engagement, Science Education, Open Access/Open Science, Gender Equality, Governance and Ethics as they have been defined by the European Commission¹⁶.

¹⁶ EU, Regulation No 1291/2013

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The participants had generated 10 ideas of actions from the very general to the very specific. These actions were classified according to the RRI dimensions. Most of them (except two) related to several RRI dimensions. The graph below (Fig.5) takes into account this multidimensional status.

Fig.5. Number of actions per RRI dimension

The participants voted Open access as the most relevant dimension involved in 9 actions. It was followed closely by Public Engagement and Governance (7 actions). Science Education came in the fourth place with 2 actions. The dimension of Ethics was associated with 1 action. No action is directly related to Gender Equality.

The figure 6 below specifies the attribution of the RRI dimensions to every action proposed by the participants during the workshop.

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Fig.6. Actions and their RRI dimensions

In Fig. 6 two actions (actions 5 and 8) are related to only one RRI dimension. Two actions (9 and 10) fell into two RRI dimensions, four (1, 2, 3 and 4) were related to three RRI dimensions and two (6 and 7) to four RRI dimensions. There were no actions associated with five or all six RRI dimensions. Consequently, it appears that even though it

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was difficult to generate actions that would unite all the RRI dimensions, most of the actions had an RRI multidimensional aspect showing that in practice, the RRI dimensions were closely interlinked.

The number of RRI dimensions per action was 2,6 in average, whereas the average number of RRI dimensions per cluster was 4 for C3:Education – Awareness, 2,6 for C2:Knowledge sharing and support systems, and 2,25 for C1:Technological solutions.

The influence map had 4,33 RRI dimensions in average. The figure 7 below shows the percentage of the RRI dimensions per cluster and the influence map. The significant percentage of Open access, Public Engagement and Governance pinpoints the critical role that the general public, policy makers and other stakeholders can play in reducing the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Open Access is a means of stimulating knowledge access and sharing by European citizens, business representatives, researchers and policy makers in order to take responsible decisions and provide safe solutions while developing or using maritime transportation services.

The absence of gender equality reveals a critical gap in access to opportunities and resources and decision-making power for women and men.

Fig.7. RRI dimensions (%) per cluster and roadmap

6.2 Who are the main target stakeholder groups of the actions?

The Fig. 8 below shows the number of actions that called for the involvement of each stakeholder group: the civil society (citizens/CSOs/NGOs), business/industry, researchers, and policy-makers. The engagement of researchers and academia was the most sought for the implementation of all the actions, followed by the business and industry sector. This goes in line with the overall character of the workshop relying significantly on the academic and industrial opinion on future maritime transportation.

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Fig.8. Number of actions per stakeholder group

The Fig. 9 below shows the stakeholder groups in charge for the implementation of the individual actions.

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Fig.9. Stakeholder groups per action

All actions were collective and required collaboration of several stakeholder groups. Six actions required the involvement of all stakeholder groups in their implementation. They were: *Promote a closer collaboration between*

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politicians and the population to increase funding for research (A7, C2, L3, V5), Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level (A6, C3, L2, V5), Promote actions at trans-national level based on a comparison among research, industry, policy makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors (A5, C2, L1, V6), Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality (A4, C2, L3, V3), Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems (A3, C1, L2, V3), and Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports(A1, C1, L3, V2).

The Fig. 10 below presents the percentage of engagement of the stakeholder groups in clusters and influence map. It confirms a balanced participation of all stakeholder groups in the implementation of the technological solutions, knowledge sharing and support systems and in promoting education. The policy makers have a low participation level in the development of the technological solutions.

Fig.10. Stakeholder groups (%) per cluster and roadmap

6.3 Engagement (public and multi-stakeholder)

The sea transportation sector lacks actions at trans-national level and needs a comparison between research, industry, policy makers and all stakeholders to develop them.

Collaboration among politicians and the population, trainers and students are needed to better meet environmental and social standards and to foster the research and innovation of practices for the socio-economic development.

Reducing the environmental impact of maritime transport requires education and training at all levels, both at school and in the companies.

Cooperation among research, industry, policy makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors allows the development of innovative technological solutions for decision support and information/infrastructure sharing.

Multi-stakeholder Engagement was a very significant dimension with 7 related actions.

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N°	CLUSTER	ACTION	VOTES
ACTIONS ON THE ROADMAP			
1	1	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	2
2	2	Sharing of infrastructures and information	1
3	1	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	3
4	2	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	3
5	2	Promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors	6
6	3	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	5
7	2	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	5

The actions suggested by the participants were based on education and collaboration/comparison among research, industry, policy makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors.

6.4 Science education

Science Education and educational activities about sustainable management of marine resources are relevant to both reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase the safety level.

The participants suggested two actions favouring Science Education

N°	CLUSTER	ACTION	VOTES
ACTIONS ON THE ROADMAP			
6	3	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level.	5
7	2	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	5

6.5 Open access

Open access to scientific data and information can also relate to the sharing of information that are necessary for developing terrestrial-maritime infrastructures, "safe by design" - driven technological solutions, information-based decision support systems, advanced ship propulsion technologies aimed at reducing the environmental impact of maritime transport and increasing safety.

Nine actions related to Open Access were defined during the workshop, making it the most significant RRI dimension.

N°	CLUSTER	ACTION	VOTES
ACTIONS ON THE ROADMAP			
1	1	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	2
2	2	Sharing of infrastructures and information	1
3	1	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	3

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4	2	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	3
6	3	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	5
7	2	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	5
8	1	Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies	3
9	2	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services	4
10	1	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks	2

6.6 Gender equality

Gender equality did not come up as the topic of the discussions of the participants. Consequently, no actions relating directly to this RRI dimensions were put forward, which did not mean that the maritime transportation should not face challenges that could negatively affect women's presence in this sector.

6.7 Governance

The critical requirement of governance for maritime transports is the active engagement of policy makers and key stakeholders whose policies and actions can significantly affect the development of a shared legislative framework that regulates maritime transportation technologies.

Governance was relevant for seven related actions. The participants believed that governance arrangements and practices were critical to favouring sustainable maritime transport and they called for a closer collaboration between politicians and the population, trainers and students.

N°	CLUSTER	ACTION	VOTES
ACTIONS ON THE ROADMAP			
1	1	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	2
2	2	Sharing of infrastructures and information	1
3	1	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	3
4	2	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	3
6	3	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	5
7	2	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	5
9	2	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services	4

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6.8 Ethics

The ethical challenges relate to respect of fundamental rights and conditions at work in the entire supply chains, to the rights of local communities to prosper and to the rights of future generations to have healthy seas and oceans with abundant resources available to all.

Only one action related to Ethics was defined during the workshop. It concerned with societal relevance and ethical acceptability of nanotechnology use for ship building.

N°	CLUSTER	ACTION	VOTES
ACTIONS ON THE ROADMAP			
10	1	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks	2

7 Workshop impact and implications for the future

7.1 Actions that can be implemented in the framework of the MARINA project

The following actions proposed by the participants can be taken up by the MARINA consortium:

Knowledge sharing and communication

- Sharing of information on maritime and non-maritime transport from a sustainability perspective;
- Providing education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level.
- Promoting a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport.
- Promote actions at trans-national level based on a comparison among research, industry, policy makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors
- RRI international conferences and call for papers on scaling up research to address the challenges of a responsible maritime transportation.

7.2 Emerging topics

During the workshop discussion the following topics emerged:

1. Marine/maritime Spatial Planning - Planning of the maritime space. Improvement of communication/coordination among the actors in the supply chain and long-term planning. Inter-organizational cooperation.
2. Security - Specific laws to support security. Synchronization of logistic services for vessels approaching the port.
3. Marine and maritime research. Increase funding for research, fishing, and transport.
4. Marine pollution/Marine litter - Use of graphene filters (already used for water desalination) to protect the potentially dangerous cargo in case of accident. Continuous monitoring of the environmental impact of ships.
5. Technology and Innovation - Infrastructure solutions (also ICT) to share a new demand for sustainable maritime and non-maritime transport systems. Promotion and support of initiatives such as BlueMed, but also national technological clusters.

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7.3 Policy implications resulting from the workshop

The main marine subjects discussed during the workshop were maritime, integrated, and intelligent transportation, with a specific focus on environmental and socio-economic impacts and security/safety of transport systems.

The actions suggested by the participants referred strongly to the need for a stronger collaboration between policy-makers and the population and to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport.

An emerging R&I topic discussed during the workshop was that of autonomous ships, which are expected to have for 2030/2050, that will be developed for urban and coastal transportation. New specific legislations are needed to manage this new kind of innovation in maritime transport systems. Moreover, a common strategy for policies involving research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors is also needed to manage the impact and the transition towards autonomous ships.

8 Workshop follow-up in my organisation

The workshop allowed for enlarging the professional network of CNR and suggested collaborative RRI-driven actions and projects that could be implemented by the research organisation in cooperation with local communities.

8.1 Actions that can be implemented

Science communication

- Dissemination and communication actions online and offline with schools and civil society of the results of the MML workshop using the Knowledge Sharing Platform for continuing the discussion on the hot topic
- Science education involving general public
- Participation to national/international events for sharing knowledge and results on the hot topic

Public engagement

- Engage communities that can contribute to the theme. These communities can be federated in the platform.
- Organise participatory workshops and seminars on hot topics related marine societal challenges.

9 Participants of the MARINA local workshop

9.1 Participant profile

Fourteen participants attended the local MML workshop in Rome. The classification of participants per stakeholder group, gender, activity sector, and age is presented in the graphs here below.

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- Participants per stakeholder group and gender

Fig.11. Participant profile breakdown

- Participant activity sector

Fig.12. Participant activity sectors in relation to the hot topic

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- Age

Fig.13. Participant age groups

9.2 Participants' personal aims to attend the workshop

At the end of the workshop an evaluation questionnaire was filled in by ten participants. Four participants left the meeting before. The results of this survey are summarised in the graphs here below.

Fig.14. Participants' personal aims to attend the MARINA workshop in Rome, Italy

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9.3 Participant knowledge of the RRI

Fig.15. Participants' understanding of the RRI before and after the workshop

Fig.16. How important is to learn about RRI

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9.4 Participant assessment of the workshop

Fig.17. Participants rating of how the different tools are relevant for them

Fig.18. Illustrations on how the participants will follow-up

10 Conclusions

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was open access. This may be due to multidisciplinary and transnationality of the issues related to maritime transport. Several disciplines are involved and open access can facilitate the mutual comprehension and collaboration.

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The chief message was the need to *promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors.* (6 votes) This aims sharing a common strategy for policies involving research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors.

Good practice

Example

During the discussions, the participants suggested good practice initiatives worth replicating such as:

1. The Rotterdam harbour: this harbour is one of the best examples of efficient harbour in the world.
2. Autonomous Ship: similarly to autonomous cars the industry is reflecting on autonomous ships and in the next decades the maritime transport will move towards this technology.
3. Graphene technology: this technology will provide filters to protect the potentially dangerous cargo in case of accident.
4. The work done in Italy to organise the Italian harbours as a national/regional harbours system with an agreement on roles, the complementarity and the exchange of information.

Workshop follow-up with participants

The workshop initial results and photographs were posted on the MARINA Knowledge Sharing Platform where the workshop participants were able to download them. The online webcasting on Youtube and MARINA platform of the workshop enabled to share the event with remote participants. The webcast is still available at <https://youtu.be/Zs8Vm5esPQQ>, and had 82 views so far.

Moreover, the extracts of this report will be published on the MARINA Knowledge Sharing Platform and shared with the workshop participants. This will be an occasion to reach out to the participants and invite them to visit the MARINA platform to retrieve it together with other international and local MML workshop reports.

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11 Appendices

11.1 Appendix 1: A list of actions and their clarifications

N	ACTION	CLARIFICATION	VOTES
1	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	<p>The focus is on the integration of maritime transport with rail transport and the land transport system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating the maritime and terrestrial transportation system should optimise costs and times for interconnecting gates in the harbours as well as ports with the hinterland. Re-designing the existing transportation network is required researches and innovation should develop new means of transport. Designing and building innovative transportation structures Improve cooperation among the different organizations and actors (Ports, policy makers, transportation authorities, companies,) Optimization of services improving the automation level 	2
2	Sharing of infrastructures and information	Designing infrastructural solutions also using ICT tools to share a new demand for maritime and non-maritime transport from a sustainability perspective	1
3	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	<p>Currently there is a strong gap in the communication/coordination among the different actors for innovation in transportations (maritime and integrated transport) and there is a strong need of planning (long term level). Improving a safe by design approach helps to integrate safety and innovation, and can involve the different actors in the process.</p>	3
4	Implementation of a Decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	Different dimensions and parameters need to be considered for including multi-disciplinarity and the different stakeholders' competences in a decision support systems for facilitating anticipate impacts and improve acceptance and sustainability of research and innovation.	3
5	Promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policy-makers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors	<p>Involving actors belonging to different sectors (technological, sociological, economic). It is crucial for having a shared strategy and the policies also built together with the countries of North Africa is underlined. The evaluation of the commitment must be based on scientific bases for the member countries of the European Union (Suez and Gibraltar). This is important for monitoring of the continuous environmental impact of ships and support infrastructures. It is also important for a careful maritime spatial planning action.</p>	
6	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact	The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and protected marine areas is fundamental for the socio-economic re-launch of Italy. The history of the Mediterranean testifies that the presence of the ports has always meant a social and cultural economic development of the	5

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	of maritime transport and increase safety, Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	territory concerned. Training is a crucial element to stimulate a shared awareness of the potential presented, even in areas such as in southern Italy, building new opportunities for a sustainable development. Education has to improve collective trainers and students perception of the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	
7	Promote a closer collaboration between policy-makers and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic development	A strong collaboration among different actors (also involving policy-makers) will allow matching the different needs and anticipating potential impacts of research and innovation. This is crucial for increasing funding for research for ports, transportation and economic activities such as phishing or touristic activities.	5
8	Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies	Competitions should be promoted to collect ideas and technological solutions. An example of solution described during the workshop is represented by the project of the advanced wind power system should provide information on the development times and expected costs of the system with the impact on propulsion costs compared to other energy sources	3
9	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services	For security and safety the existing information technologies can be exploited. For services, the lack of matching supply and demand for services, for example the synchronization of logistics services due to the approach of the vessels at the port, is a bottleneck for the economy of ports.	4
10	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks	For example it is possible to use of graphene filters to protect the environment in the event of potential dangerous cargo in case of accident.	2

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11.2 Appendix 2: Workshop implementation

Recruitment of participants

At the beginning, a research was carried out to identify experts and stakeholders whose work or interests related to maritime transportation, also related to the development of territories and spatial planning. The candidates were chosen asking for experts to APRE, to universities and companies and also involving directly the CNR network. It was defined a list of 60 potential participants.

21 confirmed their participation. 14 people actually attended at the MML as a few participants cancelled their attendance because had a sudden commitment or felt ill.

A poster campaign in English and Italian was carried out to promote the workshop in the area. The leaflet of the event was put in universities and associations locations.

Moreover, the workshop was promoted through the websites of the MARINA project.

Workshop facilitation method

The MARINA workshop “What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?”, held in Rome - Italy, started with the explanation of the methodology of the workshop facilitated with the contribution of Chiara Bolognini from ISPRA. After the explanation of the methodology and an introduction of the MARINA project, some experts introduced different relevant issues and perspectives related to the workshop topic for sharing information and facilitating the discussion of the stakeholders.

For this reason the workshop used a modified version of Science Cafe. It was facilitated engaging participants in the discussion as described in <http://www.caffescienza.it/> and in, http://www.cafescientifique.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=72&Itemid=484) for Science Cafè. However, as the MML workshop was held in a room that is located in the building of the National Research Council in Rome, we classify the used method as “Other”. We have chosen this method because it enables participants to explore a topic from multiple perspectives in a friendly manner.

Generating, clarifying and merging ideas of action

The workshop started with four experts' [presentations](#) related to the maritime transportations ([available on the MARINA knowledge sharing platform](#)). After these presentations participants started to discuss exchanging their experiences and opinions, and then they were asked to propose specific actions.

The ideas of actions revolved around the central theme of the relevance of sea transportation for innovation at all levels for the territory. No ideas were merged because they described different activities. The different actions were clustered according to the three clusters: *Technological solutions*, *Knowledge sharing and support systems*, and *Education - Awareness*.

Building a roadmap

The mapping process consisted of analysing the proposed actions, and evaluating what action is preliminary with respect to the others generating the final influence map of the actions proposed (see section 5.3). Moreover, all actions were submitted for voting and each participant voted in 3 actions, producing the results as in the table of section 5.3.

Workshop organisation

The hot topic of the workshop was chosen from the list of marine themes suggested for the MARINA project. The choice of this hot topic was related to its relevance at general level (indeed, maritime transport has a significant impact on the environment and, considering that it is cheaper than other types of transport and it represents an

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important driving force for tourism and economy, it is expected that their overall volume will continue to increase in the coming years). Its importance in the Lazio region in Italy.

The participants found the workshop interesting, as it enabled to compare different experiences and to discuss on approaches and objectives that decision makers used and will use for funding research and innovation in Italy and in Europe. Coffee, tea and cakes were served on a side counter in the room.

Workshop follow-up with participants

The workshop initial results and photographs were posted on the MARINA Knowledge Sharing Platform in the event [What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?](#). The event is also embedded in the MARINA website.

The workshop participants can download materials from the MARINA platform/website. The webcasting (done by Roberto Daffinà of ISPRA) of the discussion is also available. The results of this workshop can be discussed in the on-line chats of the event, where the participants will be invited to provide a feedback and crossing with other initiatives. The results will be also disseminated using social networks and other events.

Workshop implementation challenges

The implementation of the workshop required to clarify to the participants that the discussion and actions proposed during the workshop needed to be connected with technological challenges, but also with research and innovation challenges considering the RRI and societal dimensions.

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11.3 Appendix 3: Leaflet and Agenda of the workshop

Organizzato da:

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

MARINA
Get started in responsible marine research and innovation.

In collaborazione con:

APRE
Associazione per la Ricerca e l'Innovazione

ISPRA
Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under CA No. 710566

**COME SARÀ IL TRASPORTO MARITTIMO NEL 2050?
TRASPORTI MARITTIMI: QUALI LE SFIDE IN TERMINI DI
RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE RESPONSABILE?**

*Sfide e opportunità
Science Café*

Seminario di informazione e partecipazione sui trasporti marittimi

Discutiamo, esploriamo, proponiamo e facciamo rete

CNR, Via dei Taurini 19, Roma

La partecipazione è libera e gratuita
Per iscrizioni: marina.pro@irpps.cnr.it

14 marzo 2018
dalle 14:30

In Italia nel 2017 la modalità di trasporto di merci via mare è aumentata in termini di tonnellate del 3,4%. Il traffico portuale delle merci, a livello globale, è stato di 285 milioni di tonnellate, con un aumento del 7,4% rispetto all'anno precedente, mentre quello di cabotaggio è stato di 173 milioni di tonnellate, con una diminuzione del 2,7%. L'Italia è al terzo posto per il trasporto marittimo di merci, preceduta da Regno Unito e Paesi Bassi (Annuario Statistico Italiano 2017 - relativo all'anno 2015). E' sempre più forte la richiesta di un modello di sviluppo capace di coniugare crescita e occupazione, assicurando contemporaneamente che gli ecosistemi, e quindi anche l'ecosistema marino, siano salvaguardati. In questo contesto il Mediterraneo ha giocato storicamente e gioca un ruolo chiave per lo sviluppo culturale, sociale, economico e politico dei paesi che ne sono bagnati, e in generale per tutto il continente Europeo. Per questa ragione, nell'affrontare le sfide che il trasporto marittimo pone è fondamentale che l'impatto di valutazione ambientale risulti affiancato da una corretta e completa informazione che coinvolge la società, un'adeguata educazione scientifica e generalmente una adeguata discussione secondo i principi della ricerca e dell'innovazione responsabile, e secondo le sfide sociali che le innovazioni propongono. Ciò deve consentire un processo di sviluppo sostenibile (dal punto di vista economico, sociale e ambientale) favorendo l'accettazione delle innovazioni e delle tecnologie emergenti e consentendo uno sfruttamento del potenziale economico, sociale, culturale con particolare riguardo alle caratteristiche del Mediterraneo.

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Il progetto MARINA

Il progetto MARINA è stato finanziato dal programma H2020. E' un progetto che mira a federare le reti esistenti, le comunità, le piattaforme on-line e i servizi fornendo un ambiente che ha l'ambizione di stimolare l'impegno di ricercatori, della società civile, delle organizzazioni (CSO), dei cittadini, delle industrie, dei responsabili politici, dei comunicatori in un approccio di Ricerca e Innovazione Responsabile nei settori e sui temi collegati al mare. In particolare, il progetto identifica sfide e scenari della ricerca e dell'innovazione responsabile e le collega alle esigenze e alle sfide della società. A tal fine il progetto ha posto in atto un processo di discussione volto a generare una maggiore consapevolezza individuale e collettiva sulle questioni del mare di maggior rilievo per la società europea, integrando le esigenze e le aspettative dei cittadini con ciò che il mondo scientifico e dell'innovazione può offrire. Verranno quindi sviluppate proposte di soluzioni guidate di Ricerca e Innovazione Responsabile, nonché consigli e opzioni politiche nel settore marino a livello comunitario, nazionale e locale.

Il seminario di mobilitazione e apprendimento reciproco

COS'È IL SEMINARIO DI MOBILITAZIONE E APPRENDIMENTO RECIPROCO?

Il seminario di mobilitazione e apprendimento reciproco unisce tutti gli interessati allo sviluppo di innovazioni di successo, di soluzioni utili e politiche efficaci nel settore marino.

E' un ambiente unico che favorisce l'integrazione dei bisogni, delle aspettative e delle opinioni dei cittadini con il processo di Ricerca e Innovazione Responsabile (RRI) marina.

Tramite l'uso di metodi partecipativi e interattivi, vogliamo creare un forum per lo scambio di conoscenze, per la condivisione di buone pratiche e per la creazione di soluzioni per le sfide marine modellate sulla RRI.

Il progetto MARINA organizzerà due fasi collegate di workshop MML a livello locale ed internazionale in 14 paesi europei da novembre 2016 fino a giugno 2018.

Rimani sempre aggiornato: www.marina-project.eu

CHI PUO' PARTECIPARE?

Tutti possono partecipare al workshop MML!

Il progetto MARINA permetterà agli europei di far sentire la propria voce, da qualunque luogo provengano, dalla terra ferma e dalla costa, dalla campagna, da piccole città o da grandi metropoli.

PERCHE' DOVREI PARTECIPARE?

Per essere sicuro che le mie necessità, aspettative e visioni vengano tenute in conto quando verranno prese decisioni e sviluppate innovazioni a livello locale, nazionale ed europeo sull'ambiente marino.

Per usare la mia creatività affinché nuove soluzioni marine aiutino al meglio la società europea ma anche le comunità locali e i singoli cittadini.

Per far parte della comunità europea sulla Ricerca ed Innovazione Responsabile.

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AGENDA

COME SARÀ IL TRASPORTO MARITTIMO NEL 2050? TRASPORTI MARITTIMI: QUALI LE SFIDE IN TERMINI DI RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE RESPONSABILE?

14 Marzo

Via dei Taurini 19, Roma

Introduzione ai lavori della giornata 14,00

Chiara BOLOGINI

ISPRA

Fernando FERRI

CNR

PRESENTAZIONE DEL PROGETTO MARINA

Presentazioni 14,30 (5 min. per presentazione)

Elena CIAPPI

CNR-INSEAN Progetto Bluemed

Francesco FILIPPI

Centro di Ricerca per il Trasporto e la Logistica, univ. di Roma la Sapienza

Filippo MARINI

Capitaneria di Porto di Fiumicino

Andrea POLCARI, Sesto VITICOLI

AIRI

Caffè 14,50

Discussione 15,20

Definizione delle idee 16,20

Esposizione delle idee 17,00

Votazione 17,40

CONCLUSIONI e questionario di gradimento 18,10

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11.4 Appendix 4: List of communication materials about the workshop

1. [MARINA Project leaflet in Italian and in English](#)
2. [Leaflet of the event in Italian](#)
3. [Hot topic brochure](#)

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11.5 Appendix 5: List of audio-visual material about the workshop

1. Webcast (available in the platform in the event "[“COME SARÀ IL TRASPORTO MARITTIMO NEL 2050? TRASPORTI MARITTIMI: QUALI LE SFIDE IN TERMINI DI RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE RESPONSABILE?”](#)")
2. Pictures: under "[“COME SARÀ IL TRASPORTO MARITTIMO NEL 2050? TRASPORTI MARITTIMI: QUALI LE SFIDE IN TERMINI DI RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE RESPONSABILE?”](#)" event in the event section on the MARINA platform

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